

Effects of Compounds as Diffusion-Barrier Coatings between the Fiber and the Matrix in Tungsten Fiber Reinforced Nickel Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

A study of coatings on fiber which can effectively produce chemical compatibility between fiber and matrix in tungsten fiber reinforced nickel matrix composites was conducted. Activated reactive evaporation deposited coatings with a thickness of 1 to 4 μm such compounds as ZrC, ZrO_2 , HfC, HfO_2 , TaC, Al_4C_3 and TiC were applied to W fiber of 500 μm in diameter.

Both coated and uncoated fibers were embedded and hot-pressed in -400 mesh carbonyl Ni powder under a pressure of 35 MPa in argon atmosphere for 2hrs at 500°, 900°, and 1100° C, respectively.

Both coated and uncoated W fiber-Ni composites were exposed for some period of time up to 200hrs at 1150° C. The composites thus exposed were examined for the microstructural stability of the W fiber and the fiber-matrix interface by means of optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, and electron probe X-ray microanalysis. Four-point bending tests were also carried out.

In uncoated W fiber-Ni composites exposed at 1150° C, a compound layer at the fiber-matrix interface was formed gradually with a period of time up to 50hrs. The layer then begins to diffuse into Ni matrix with an increase of exposure time and eventually is decomposed completely after 200hrs exposure. Diffusion zone in the vicinity of the compound layer was detected to increase with exposure time. On the other hand, recrystallization was observed at outer circumferential region of fiber after 200hrs exposure.

In contrast to the uncoated W fiber-Ni composites, most of coated W fiber-Ni composites appeared to be relatively effective in eliminating or retarding interfacial reaction. Among all the barrier-coatings, ZrC and ZrO_2 coatings proved to be considerably effective in comparison with the others.

In the bending strength of the composites exposed for some period up to 200 hrs, the coated W fiber-Ni composites showed little change of strength, whereas the uncoated W fiber-Ni composites showed the rapid reduction of strength after 200hrs exposure: The case of the latter is primarily attributed to secondary recrystallization of fiber.

INTRODUCTION

In tungsten fiber reinforced nickel alloy matrix composites, chemical incompatibility between fiber and matrix usually takes place during fabrication or subsequent service at elevated temperatures.

It has been known that mechanical properties of the composites are drastically reduced due to various types of interfacial reactions such as the formation of brittle reaction layer (1-4), recrystallization of fiber (5-7), and the area reduction of fiber.

Up to date, several approaches have been done to improve the compatibility between fiber and matrix : For example, control of matrix composition, optimization of fabrication process, and diffusion-barrier coating on fiber are included.

Among these approaches, the potential utility of diffusion-barrier coatings of appropriate compounds such as oxides, carbides, and nitrides on W fiber in Ni alloy matrix composites has been examined (8-10).

From the above reports, it is concluded that: 1) among matrix elements such as Ni, Fe, and Co, pure Ni is the most active element in enhancing recrystallization of W fiber. 2) the microstructural stability of pure W fiber without coating is relatively poor at elevated temperatures compared to that of W fiber doped with ThO₂. 3) success in development of barrier-coatings in limiting interfacial reactions depends on a suitable coating method on fiber and optimum selection of coatings.

The major objective of the present work is to improve the compatibility by the use of physio-chemical effects of oxides and carbides as diffusion-barrier coatings. Microstructure variations at the periphery of interface and mechanical properties of the composites were investigated in relation to coatings.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The W fiber reinforced Ni matrix composites was prepared from W fiber of 500 μm diameter with purity of 99.97% and carbonyl Ni powder with a particle of -400 mesh and purity of 99.97%. The barrier-coatings used are refractory compounds such as ZrC, ZrO₂, HfC, HfO₂, TaC, Al₄C₃ and TiC.

Coating procedure

The as-drawn W fibers of approximately 110 mm long were straightened and cleaned by electropolishing in 98% water + 2% NaOH solution. Coating on the fibers was conducted by activated reactive evaporation (ARE) process using electron beam type physical vapor deposition techniques (Ion-plating). Pure metals such as Zr, Hf, Ta, Al and Ti are evaporated in the presence of a partial pressure (1-3x10⁻⁴Torr) of reactive gas (O₂ or C₂H₂) to form the corresponding compounds on the fibers. Uniform thickness of coating layer on fiber surfaces was accomplished by rotating the fibers that are located at the periphery of two wheels with 100 mm diameter. X-ray diffraction revealed the presence of a extremely small amount of pure metal element in some of deposited substances such as oxides and carbides.

Specimen fabrication and thermal exposure

Ni matrix green of 1.5 mm thick was obtained under a pressure of 35 MPa at room temperature. Both uncoated and coated fibers were cut into length of 40 mm corresponding to the intended specimen length. The layers of unidirectionally arranged fibers were alternatively embedded in layers of Ni matrix green. The Ni matrix green thus composed with the fibers was hot-pressed under a pressure of 35 MPa in argon atmosphere for 2hrs. The sintering temperatures were 500°C for Uncoated, HfC and HfO₂, 900°C for TaC, TiC and Al₄C₃, 1100°C for ZrC and ZrO₂ coated fibers, respectively. The fiber volume fraction of the specimen was about 11%. The specimens for bending test were machined to 40 mm long, 4 mm square. The specimens were exposed for some defined periods of time up to 200hrs at 1150°C in argon atmosphere using siliconite electric furnace.

Evaluation of microstructure

Metallographic observations and chemical analysis of the microstructure at the periphery of interface were conducted by means of optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and electron probe X-ray microanalysis, respectively. The effectiveness of barrier-coatings was evaluated by the comparison of the individual thickness of reaction zone such as compound layer, diffusion zone of W in Ni matrix, recrystallization zone of fiber.

Static four-point bending tests

The four-point bending tests at room temperature were made for the composites with ZrC and ZrO₂ coated fibers on an Instron type machine at a cross head speed of 1 mm per min. In addition, the uncoated W fiber-Ni composites were tested for a reference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Uncoated fibers

During hot-pressing, no reaction at interface between fiber and matrix was observed as shown in Figure 1(a). After 100hrs exposure at 1150°C, a thick compound layer and extensive diffusion zone were found at the periphery of interface as shown in Figure 1(b), (d). In this case, no recrystallization of fiber was detected. After 200hrs exposure, recrystallization zone of approximately 45 μm thick was found at outer circumferential region of fiber as shown in Figure 1(c), accompanied with the complete decomposition of the compound layer which was detected after 100hrs exposure. The compound layer seems to be a metastable intermetallic compound, since no intermetallic compound is stable at temperatures above 1040°C in W-Ni system (11) and the compound layer tends to decompose with an increase of exposure time after 50hrs.

Figure 1. Microstructures and line profile at the periphery of uncoated W fibers in Ni matrix. (a) as hot-pressed, (b) 100hrs, (c) 200hrs, (d) 100hrs at 1150°C.

ZrC and ZrO₂-coated fibers

In the as hot-pressed composites, ZrC and ZrO₂ coating layers on fibers were both uniform and about 4 μm in thickness. Both coating layers at interface between fiber and matrix were well bonded as presented in Figure 2(a), (b).

After 200hrs exposure, no reaction was observed at both interfaces of fiber-barrier and matrix-barrier in ZrO_2 -coated W fiber-Ni composites, whereas a small amount of reaction, forming a compound layer, was detected at interface between fiber and barrier in ZrC-coated W fiber-Ni composites as shown in Figure 2(d), (c).

Figure 2. Microstructures of W fibers with ZrC and ZrO_2 coatings in Ni matrix. (a), (b) as hot-pressed, (c), (d) exposed for 200hrs at $1150^\circ C$.

Backscatter electron and X-ray images of ZrO_2 -coated W fiber-Ni samples exposed for 200hrs are shown in Figure 3. No morphological change of ZrO_2 coating layer and non of mutual diffusion between W and Ni was detected as illustrated Figure 3(a), (b), (c) and (d).

Figure 3. Electron-probe X-ray images at the interface between ZrO_2 -coated W fiber and Ni matrix after exposure for 200hrs at $1150^\circ C$.

HfC and HfO₂ coatings

In as hot-pressed conditions, the HfC coating layer with a thickness of 3 μm appears to be well bonded as shown in Figure 4(a). After 50hrs exposure at 1150°C, no interfacial reaction occurred, whereas after 100hrs exposure, recrystallization zone of about 42 μm thick was observed at the outer circumferential region of fiber as shown in Figure 4(b).

The effect of HfO₂ coatings on recrystallization also was almost similar with the HfC coatings. The effect of HfO₂ coating on W fiber as a barrier to reaction was less than that of HfC coatings.

TaC and Al₄C₃ coatings

In as hot-pressed conditions, the thicknesses of TaC and Al₄C₃ coating layers on W fiber were both less than 1 μm . For both coatings, compound layer was formed at the fiber-barrier interface during hot-pressing as shown in Figure 5(a) and (b).

For the composites with TaC-coated W fiber, a remarkable growth of the compound layer with exposure time was observed as shown in Figure 5(c). In this case, microcracks appeared in the compound layer, but no recrystallization in fiber was detected.

For the composites with Al₄C₃-coated W fiber, a compound layer of about 14 μm thick appeared at interface between fiber and barrier after 200hrs exposure as shown in Figure 5(d). However, recrystallization of fiber and extensive diffusion zone of W in Ni matrix were found in region where the compound is absent.

Figure 5. Microstructures of coated W fibers in matrix. (a), (b) as hot-pressed, (c), (d) 200hrs at 1150°C.

TiC coatings

In as hot-pressed conditions, the thickness of the TiC coating layer was about 3 μm . No interfacial reaction took place in hot-pressing process as shown in Figure 6(a). After 200hrs exposure, a compound layer of approximately 20 μm deep was observed at interface between fiber and barrier as shown in Figure 6(b).

Figure 6. Microstructures of TiC-coated fibers in Ni matrix. (a) as hot-pressed, (b) exposed for 200hrs at 1150°C.

Thicknesses of reaction zone vs. high temperature exposure

The thicknesses of reaction zone for Ni base composites reinforced by W fiber with several coatings are listed in Table 1. Most of the coatings are effective against interfacial reactions at elevated temperatures. Among all the coatings, ZrC and ZrO₂ work as the most effective barrier, which maintain integrity up to 200hrs.

Table 1. Thickness of reaction zone in Ni base composites with coated and uncoated W fibers after exposure at 1150°C.

Time (hrs)	R.Z	Diffusion-barrier coatings (μm)							
		Uncoated	ZrC	ZrO ₂	HfC	HfO ₂	TaC	Al ₄ C ₃	TiC
As hot-pressed	C	0	0	0	0	0	4	3	0
	D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	R	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	C	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	D	35	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	R	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	C	-	-	-	-	-	25	5	7
	D	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
	R	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
50	C	38	0	0	0	0	-	-	-
	D	77	0	0	0	0	-	-	-
	R	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-
100	C	25	3	0	0	0	35	8	10
	D	135	0	0	0	0	34	0	0
	R	0	0	0	42	12	0	0	0
200	C	0	7	0	-	-	50	14 (0)	20
	D	192	0	0	-	-	80	0 (36)	0
	R	45	0	0	-	-	0	0 (40)	0

C: compound layer

D: diffusion zone of W in Ni matrix

R: recrystallization zone (): reaction zone without compound

Bending tests

The results of the bending tests of composites at room temperature are listed in Table 2. Uncoated W fiber -Ni composites exhibited a drastic reduction in strength for the exposure time of up to 10hrs, then maintained a constant strength until a rapid reduction in strength was observed after 200hrs exposure. In as hot-pressed conditions, the strength of composites with ZrC and ZrO₂ coated fibers is both smaller compared with that of uncoated W fiber-Ni composites, whereas after 200hrs exposure, the strength of composites with ZrC and ZrO₂ coated fibers is larger than that of composites with uncoated W fiber. The strength of the composites with ZrO₂ coated W fiber is somewhat higher than that of ZrC coatings.

Table 2. The R.T four-point bending strength of Ni base composites with coated and uncoated W fibers after exposure at 1150°C.

Time (hrs)	Bending strength (Kg/mm ²)		
	Uncoated	ZrC-coated	ZrO ₂ -coated
As hot-pressed	126	68	82
10	76	-	-
50	71	64	75
100	68	67	72
200	49	63	70

All of uncoated W fiber-Ni composites were fractured, whereas most of coated W fiber-Ni composites were not fractured with few exception and breaking behaviors were characterized by the protrusion mode of fibers in both ends of compression side of the composites. Some of tested specimens are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The appearances of the bending-tested specimens after exposure for 200hrs at 1150°C. (a) with uncoated fibers, (b) with ZrC coated fibers, (c) with ZrO₂ coated fibers.

In non-exposed composites with uncoated fiber, separation between fiber and matrix was hardly observed. After 100hrs exposure, a remarkable debonding was found at interface between fiber and compound and W fiber failed in a brittle manner. After 200 hrs exposure, the fracture surface of fiber, accompanied by recrystallization zone of approximately 45 μm deep, was characterized by brittle failure as shown in Figure 8(a). In the fracture surface of ZrC-coated W fiber -Ni composites with 200hrs exposure, debonding was observed to occur at interface between compound layer and coatings as presented in Figure 8(b).

The difference in bending strength between non-exposed composites coated and uncoated fibers may be attributed to the changes of fiber properties due to the differences of fabricating condition. The hardness was Hv 450 and 600 for coated and uncoated fibers in as hot-pressed composites, respectively. The strength of the W fiber-Ni composite exposed at elevated temperatures appeared to be influenced by primary and secondary recrystallization of fibers. The protrusion of fibers in both ends of the composites with coated W fiber may be primarily attributed to a poor bonding in the interface.

CONCLUSION

Effects of coating of oxides and carbides on W fibers as diffusion barrier between fiber and matrix at elevated temperatures were investigated for Ni base composites. Bending tests were also carried out at room temperature for composites with both coated and uncoated fibers.

The results obtained are summarized as follows;

- (1) In composites with uncoated fiber, a thick compound layer and extensive diffusion zone of W in Ni matrix were found in the vicinity of interface after 100hrs exposure. After 200hrs exposure, recrystallization zone of approximately 45 μm thick, followed by the complete decomposition of the compound

Figure 8. SEM photographs of fracture surface in the vicinity of W fiber in Ni base composites after exposure for 200hrs at 1150°C.

layer which was detected after 100hrs exposure, was found at outer circumferential region of fiber. Extensive diffusion zone of W was found in Ni matrix.

- (2) In contrast to uncoated W fiber-Ni composites, most of coatings on W fibers appeared to be relatively effective in eliminating or retarding interfacial reactions. Among all the barrier-coatings, ZrC and ZrO₂ proved to be most effective in comparison with the others.
- (3) In comparison with the composites with uncoated W fiber, the reduction of bending strength of composites with coated fibers was extremely small after long-term exposure. This would be due to the retention of fiber property like microstructural stability at elevated temperatures.

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